

**Linkage of in situ ruminal degradation of crude protein
with ruminal degradation of amino acids and phytate
from different soybean meals in dairy cows**

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Supplementary Table 1. Chemical protein fractions¹ in soybean meal variants (% CP).

Variant no.	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
A	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.5	1.3	4.7	0.3	0.0	5.2	2.7	1.6	0.0	4.5	0.0	0.1	4.0
B1	7.1	7.3	0.3	14	20	9.4	11	6.5	7.7	1.2	3.1	13	13	12	17	14	5.5
B2	86	83	85	79	75	80	80	84	83	71	80	79	81	78	79	76	78
B3	5.0	9.3	14	6.7	3.4	7.8	3.8	7.9	7.9	21	12	5.4	5.0	4.5	3.0	8.5	11
C	1.3	0.8	1.2	0.9	1.1	1.2	1.0	1.1	1.0	1.8	1.6	1.2	1.3	1.0	0.9	1.2	1.5

¹A, NPN; B1, true protein rapidly degradable in the rumen; B2, true protein with intermediate degradation rate in the rumen; B3, true protein with slow degradation rate in the rumen; C, unavailable or cell wall-bound true protein.

Supplementary Table 2. Water solubility and estimated in situ degradation parameters of CP, CPED₆, RUP₆₁ (% CP, unless otherwise stated), and intestinal digestibility of RUP (ID_{RUP})² for soybean meal variants (n = 3 cows).

Variant no.	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	SED ³
Water solubility	3.6	3.6	2.4	6.0	3.9	3.0	2.5	5.2	2.8	2.1	2.7	2.4	4.1	4.6	4.1	5.2	3.4	.
a	4.0 ^f	7.0 ^{cd}	3.0 ^f	8.7 ^{ab}	3.0 ^f	2.7 ^{fg}	4.0 ^f	8.9 ^{ab}	4.0 ^f	0.0 ^h	1.0 ^h	5.7 ^{de}	9.0 ^a	4.2 ^{ef}	3.4 ^f	7.4 ^{bc}	1.3 ^{gh}	0.4
b	96 ^{cd}	93 ^{fg}	97 ^{cd}	91 ^{hi}	97 ^{cd}	97 ^{bc}	96 ^{cd}	91 ⁱ	96 ^{cd}	100 ^a	99 ^a	94 ^{ef}	91 ⁱ	96 ^{de}	97 ^{cd}	93 ^{gh}	99 ^{ab}	0.4
Lag (h)	1.3 ^{bc}	1.4 ^{ac}	2.0 ^a	1.9 ^{ab}	1.4 ^{ac}	1.6 ^{ac}	1.1 ^c	1.7 ^{ac}	1.4 ^{bc}	2.0 ^a	2.0 ^a	1.6 ^{ac}	1.5 ^{ac}	1.8 ^{ab}	1.8 ^{ac}	1.8 ^{ab}	1.8 ^{ab}	0.2
c (% h ⁻¹)	11 ^{bd}	9.2 ^{de}	5.7 ^f	11 ^{bc}	12 ^{ab}	10 ^{cde}	10 ^{bd}	11 ^{bd}	11 ^{bd}	4.5 ^f	6.3 ^f	14 ^a	14 ^a	11 ^{bd}	12 ^{bc}	10 ^{cde}	8.5 ^e	0.5
CPED ₆	61 ^{bc}	58 ^{cd}	45 ^f	62 ^{bc}	62 ^{bd}	58 ^c	61 ^{bc}	62 ^{bc}	61 ^{bc}	38 ^g	46 ^f	65 ^{ab}	67 ^a	59 ^{cd}	61 ^{bc}	60 ^{cd}	53 ^e	1.1
RUP ₆	39 ^{ef}	42 ^{de}	55 ^b	38 ^{ef}	38 ^{df}	42 ^e	39 ^{ef}	38 ^{ef}	39 ^{ef}	62 ^a	54 ^b	35 ^{fg}	33 ^g	41 ^{de}	39 ^{ef}	40 ^{de}	47 ^c	1.1
ID _{RUP}	96 ^a	94 ^{ab}	95 ^a	95 ^{ab}	91 ^{bcd}	93 ^{ab}	93 ^{ab}	94 ^{ab}	93 ^{ac}	94 ^{ab}	95 ^a	90 ^{cd}	87 ^d	93 ^{ab}	93 ^{ab}	95 ^{ab}	94 ^{ab}	1.1

^{a-i}Estimates with at least one identical letter were not significantly different from each other within a row ($P < 0.05$).

¹Water solubility determined with filter paper; *a* = rapidly degradable fraction; *b* = slowly degradable fraction; *c* = degradation rate; CPED₆ = calculated effective degradation of CP at a rumen passage rate of 6% h⁻¹; RUP₆ = calculated rumen-undegradable CP at a rumen passage rate of 6% h⁻¹.

²ID_{RUP} = Intestinal digestibility of RUP after 16 h incubation in the rumen.

³SED = standard error of a difference.

Supplementary Table 3. In situ degradation of CP and AA after 16 h in soybean meal variants (n = 3 cows).

Variant no	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	SED ²
Degradability (%)																		
CP	82 ^{cdf}	83 ^{bcd}	62 ^g	91 ^{ab}	88 ^{ad}	81 ^{cdf}	80 ^{df}	89 ^{ac}	90 ^{ac}	44 ^h	57 ^g	91 ^{ab}	96 ^a	83 ^{bcd}	88 ^{ad}	78 ^{ef}	75 ^f	2.3
TAA	81 ^{de}	83 ^{bde}	63 ^g	91 ^{ab}	87 ^{bcd}	81 ^{de}	78 ^{ef}	89 ^{acd}	89 ^{ad}	33 ⁱ	50 ^h	91 ^{ab}	96 ^a	80 ^{cef}	87 ^{acd}	74 ^{ef}	71 ^{fg}	2.5
Ala	79 ^{cd}	81 ^{bcd}	62 ^f	90 ^{ab}	87 ^{ac}	80 ^{cd}	76 ^{de}	88 ^{ac}	89 ^{ac}	32 ^h	48 ^g	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{cd}	87 ^{ac}	73 ^{de}	69 ^{ef}	2.5
Arg	81 ^{cdf}	83 ^{bcd}	64 ^g	91 ^{ab}	88 ^{bcd}	81 ^{cdf}	80 ^{df}	89 ^{ac}	91 ^{ab}	36 ⁱ	52 ^h	91 ^{ab}	97 ^a	82 ^{cde}	89 ^{ad}	77 ^{ef}	73 ^f	2.3
Asx ¹	80 ^{de}	82 ^{bde}	62 ^g	91 ^{ab}	87 ^{bcd}	81 ^{de}	78 ^{ef}	89 ^{acd}	90 ^{ad}	32 ⁱ	49 ^h	91 ^{ab}	97 ^a	80 ^{ce}	87 ^{acd}	74 ^{ef}	71 ^{fg}	2.5
Cys	79 ^{cef}	82 ^{bde}	63 ^g	91 ^{ab}	87 ^{acd}	80 ^{df}	76 ^{ef}	88 ^{acd}	89 ^{ad}	38 ⁱ	52 ^h	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	80 ^{de}	88 ^{acd}	74 ^{ef}	71 ^{fg}	2.5
Glx ¹	84 ^{bce}	84 ^{bce}	66 ^g	92 ^{ab}	89 ^{acd}	83 ^{ce}	80 ^{ef}	90 ^{ac}	90 ^{ac}	34 ⁱ	51 ^h	92 ^{ab}	97 ^a	82 ^{de}	89 ^{acd}	76 ^{ef}	73 ^{fg}	2.3
Gly	79 ^{ce}	81 ^{bcd}	62 ^f	90 ^{ab}	86 ^{bc}	79 ^{cd}	75 ^{de}	88 ^{ac}	88 ^{ac}	32 ^h	48 ^g	89 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{cd}	86 ^{ac}	73 ^{de}	70 ^{ef}	2.5
His	81 ^{deg}	83 ^{bcef}	63 ^h	91 ^{ab}	88 ^{acd}	82 ^{cef}	78 ^{eg}	89 ^{acd}	90 ^{acd}	34 ^j	51 ⁱ	91 ^{ac}	97 ^a	81 ^{def}	87 ^{bce}	75 ^{fg}	72 ^{gh}	2.4
Ile	82 ^{cef}	83 ^{bce}	66 ^h	91 ^{ab}	88 ^{acd}	81 ^{cef}	77 ^{eg}	89 ^{ac}	89 ^{ac}	35 ^j	49 ⁱ	91 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{deg}	87 ^{acd}	73 ^{fgh}	70 ^{gh}	2.5
Leu	79 ^{de}	81 ^{bce}	61 ^g	90 ^{ab}	86 ^{bed}	79 ^{ce}	76 ^{ef}	88 ^{acd}	89 ^{ac}	31 ⁱ	47 ^h	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{de}	87 ^{bcd}	72 ^{ef}	69 ^{fg}	2.5
Lys	82 ^{de}	83 ^{bce}	66 ^g	91 ^{ab}	88 ^{bcd}	82 ^{ce}	79 ^{ef}	89 ^{acd}	90 ^{ac}	37 ⁱ	53 ^h	91 ^{ab}	97 ^a	82 ^{de}	88 ^{bcd}	76 ^{ef}	73 ^{fg}	2.2
Met	79 ^{de}	81 ^{bce}	61 ^g	90 ^{ab}	87 ^{bcd}	80 ^{ce}	77 ^{cf}	88 ^{acd}	89 ^{ac}	34 ⁱ	49 ^h	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{de}	86 ^{acd}	72 ^{ef}	69 ^{fg}	2.6
Phe	82 ^{cef}	84 ^{bce}	66 ^h	91 ^{ab}	88 ^{ac}	82 ^{cef}	77 ^{eg}	90 ^{ac}	89 ^{ac}	31 ^j	48 ⁱ	91 ^{ab}	97 ^a	79 ^{def}	87 ^{bcd}	73 ^{fgh}	70 ^{gh}	2.5
Pro	80 ^{cf}	82 ^{bcd}	63 ^g	91 ^{ab}	87 ^{bcd}	80 ^{cf}	78 ^{df}	89 ^{ac}	89 ^{ac}	37 ⁱ	53 ^h	91 ^{ab}	97 ^a	81 ^{cf}	87 ^{bc}	75 ^{ef}	73 ^f	2.4
Ser	77 ^{def}	80 ^{bce}	57 ^g	89 ^{ab}	86 ^{bed}	78 ^{def}	76 ^{ef}	87 ^{acd}	88 ^{ac}	28 ⁱ	46 ^h	89 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{ce}	86 ^{bcd}	72 ^{ef}	69 ^f	2.7
Thr	80 ^{def}	82 ^{bde}	63 ^h	91 ^{ab}	87 ^{acd}	80 ^{def}	75 ^{eg}	88 ^{acd}	89 ^{ad}	31 ^j	47 ⁱ	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{cef}	86 ^{bcd}	73 ^{fg}	69 ^{gh}	2.5
Tyr	79 ^{cd}	81 ^{bcd}	62 ^f	90 ^{ab}	86 ^{ac}	80 ^{cd}	76 ^{de}	88 ^{ac}	89 ^{ac}	31 ^h	47 ^g	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{cd}	87 ^{ac}	73 ^{de}	69 ^{ef}	2.6
Val	79 ^{ce}	81 ^{bcd}	62 ^f	90 ^{ab}	86 ^{bc}	79 ^{ce}	76 ^{de}	88 ^{ac}	89 ^{ab}	36 ^h	50 ^g	90 ^{ab}	96 ^a	79 ^{ce}	87 ^{ac}	73 ^{de}	70 ^{ef}	2.6
Undegraded AAi/TAA ³																		
Ala	1.08 ^{ac}	1.08 ^{ab}	1.05 ^{de}	1.07 ^{ac}	1.06 ^{ce}	1.06 ^{de}	1.09 ^a	1.11 ^a	1.08 ^{ab}	1.03 ^f	1.04 ^{ef}	1.07 ^{bcd}	1.09 ^a	1.05 ^{de}	1.04 ^{def}	1.06 ^{ce}	1.06 ^{de}	0.007
Arg	0.97 ^{ab}	0.97 ^{ab}	0.98 ^a	0.97 ^{ab}	0.98 ^a	0.99 ^a	0.88 ^{ce}	0.95 ^b	0.88 ^{de}	0.96 ^{ab}	0.95 ^b	0.98 ^a	0.87 ^c	0.91 ^c	0.90 ^{cd}	0.90 ^{cd}	0.91 ^c	0.008
Asx ¹	1.02 ^{ab}	1.03 ^a	1.04 ^a	1.02 ^{ac}	1.02 ^{ac}	1.01 ^{ac}	1.00 ^{cd}	1.01 ^{ac}	0.99 ^{de}	1.02 ^{ab}	1.01 ^{ac}	1.02 ^{ac}	0.98 ^e	1.01 ^{ac}	1.00 ^{bcd}	1.01 ^{ac}	1.01 ^{ac}	0.007
Cys	1.09 ^{bc}	1.02 ^{def}	1.02 ^{def}	1.03 ^{cdef}	1.04 ^{cde}	1.04 ^{cde}	1.06 ^{cd}	1.11 ^{ab}	1.05 ^{cde}	0.93 ^h	0.95 ^{gh}	1.08 ^{bd}	1.16 ^a	1.00 ^{eg}	0.97 ^{fgh}	1.03 ^{def}	1.00 ^{eg}	0.015
Glx ¹	0.86 ^{gh}	0.89 ^{defg}	0.92 ^{bc}	0.89 ^{defg}	0.88 ^{efh}	0.88 ^{fh}	0.90 ^{cf}	0.86 ^h	0.90 ^{cf}	0.99 ^a	0.97 ^a	0.87 ^{fh}	0.88 ^{gh}	0.93 ^{bc}	0.91 ^{bce}	0.92 ^{bcd}	0.94 ^b	0.009
Gly	1.11 ^{bc}	1.06 ^{bc}	1.04 ^{cd}	1.10 ^{bc}	1.09 ^{bc}	1.10 ^{bc}	1.11 ^{bc}	1.11 ^{bd}	1.15 ^b	1.01 ^c	1.02 ^{cd}	1.15 ^b	1.25 ^a	1.07 ^{bc}	1.09 ^{bc}	1.04 ^{cd}	1.04 ^{cd}	0.028
His	1.00 ^{ab}	0.97 ^{ac}	1.00 ^{ab}	0.96 ^c	0.96 ^{bc}	0.97 ^{ac}	0.98 ^{ac}	0.96 ^{bc}	0.99 ^{ac}	0.99 ^{ac}	0.96 ^{bc}	0.99 ^{ac}	0.95 ^{bc}	0.95 ^c	1.01 ^a	0.96 ^{bc}	0.96 ^{bc}	0.012

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Supplementary Table 3. Continuation

Variant no	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	SED ²
Undegraded AAi/TAA ³																		
Ile	0.95 ^{eg}	0.95 ^{fg}	0.94 ^g	0.95 ^{fg}	0.99 ^{bcd^{ef}}	0.98 ^{dg}	1.03 ^{acd}	0.98 ^{cg}	1.02 ^{acd}	0.97 ^{dg}	1.01 ^{acdf}	0.96 ^{fg}	1.04 ^{ac}	1.05 ^a	1.01 ^{acdef}	1.05 ^{ab}	1.03 ^{ac}	0.015
Leu	1.09 ^a	1.07 ^{ab}	1.06 ^{bde}	1.08 ^{ac}	1.07 ^{ab}	1.08 ^{ab}	1.06 ^{df}	1.09 ^a	1.05 ^{efg}	1.04 ^{fg}	1.05 ^{efg}	1.07 ^{bcd^e}	1.04 ^g	1.07 ^{ad}	1.07 ^{ad}	1.08 ^{ab}	1.07 ^{bcd^e}	0.005
Lys	0.96 ^b	0.95 ^b	0.93 ^{bd}	0.94 ^{bd}	0.94 ^{bd}	0.96 ^b	0.95 ^{bd}	0.96 ^b	0.95 ^{bc}	0.94 ^{bd}	0.94 ^{bd}	0.96 ^b	0.99 ^a	0.93 ^{cd}	0.95 ^{bd}	0.93 ^d	0.94 ^{bd}	0.007
Met	1.10 ^{ab}	1.07 ^{cd}	1.06 ^{de}	1.07 ^{ce}	1.07 ^{cd}	1.07 ^{ce}	1.04 ^{ef}	1.10 ^a	1.02 ^{fg}	0.99 ^g	1.01 ^{fg}	1.09 ^{ac}	1.10 ^{ab}	1.05 ^{de}	1.08 ^{bcd}	1.09 ^{ac}	1.07 ^{cd}	0.007
Phe	0.94 ^c	0.93 ^c	0.93 ^c	0.94 ^c	0.94 ^c	0.93 ^c	1.03 ^a	0.93 ^c	1.03 ^a	1.03 ^a	1.03 ^a	0.92 ^c	0.98 ^c	1.04 ^a	1.04 ^a	1.04 ^a	1.03 ^a	0.006
Pro	1.02 ^{ab}	1.01 ^{ac}	1.02 ^a	1.02 ^a	1.03 ^a	1.03 ^a	0.99 ^{bcd}	1.01 ^{ac}	1.02 ^{ab}	0.95 ^{ef}	0.93 ^f	1.02 ^a	0.98 ^{cd}	0.95 ^{ef}	1.02 ^a	0.96 ^{de}	0.94 ^{ef}	0.007
Ser	1.18 ^a	1.15 ^{ab}	1.16 ^{ab}	1.18 ^a	1.13 ^{bcd}	1.15 ^{ac}	1.09 ^e	1.16 ^{ab}	1.10 ^{de}	1.07 ^e	1.07 ^e	1.17 ^{ab}	1.09 ^{de}	1.07 ^e	1.11 ^{ce}	1.08 ^e	1.08 ^e	0.011
Thr	1.06 ^{bde}	1.03 ^{efg}	1.02 ^g	1.04 ^{efg}	1.02 ^{gh}	1.03 ^{gh}	1.10 ^a	1.05 ^{bde}	1.08 ^{ab}	1.03 ^{fg}	1.05 ^{d^{fh}}	1.04 ^{efg}	1.07 ^{bd}	1.05 ^{cdf}	1.08 ^{bc}	1.07 ^{bd}	1.06 ^{bde}	0.006
Tyr	1.07 ^{bd}	1.08 ^{bc}	1.04 ^{cd}	1.07 ^{bc}	1.08 ^{bc}	1.06 ^{bd}	1.08 ^{bc}	1.08 ^b	1.08 ^{ab}	1.03 ^d	1.06 ^{bd}	1.06 ^{bd}	1.11 ^a	1.07 ^{bc}	1.07 ^{bc}	1.06 ^{bd}	1.07 ^{bd}	0.012
Val	1.07 ^{bde}	1.07 ^{bde}	1.04 ^{df}	1.08 ^{bd}	1.12 ^b	1.10 ^{bd}	1.07 ^{bde}	1.11 ^{ab}	1.05 ^{ade}	0.96 ^g	0.99 ^{fg}	1.09 ^{bd}	1.10 ^{abc}	1.07 ^{bde}	1.02 ^{efg}	1.04 ^{cdf}	1.02 ^{efg}	0.017

^{a-j} Estimates with at least one identical letter were not significantly different from each other within a row ($P < 0.05$)

¹Asp, Asn, and Glu, Gln, respectively, were detected together because the Asn and Gln side groups were lost during acid hydrolysis (Fontaine, 2003)

²SED = standard error of a difference.

³Ratio of undegraded AAi to TAA was calculated according to White et al. (2017).

Supplementary Figure 1

¹Asp, Asn, and Glu, Gln, respectively, were detected together because the Asn and Gln side groups were lost during acid hydrolysis (Fontaine, 2003)

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Supplementary Figure 1. Diagnostic plots for predictions of ruminal degradation of individual AA from the degradation of CP after 16 h ruminal incubation. Filled symbols and solid lines represent observed versus predicted data, and clear symbols with broken lines represent studentized residuals versus predicted data. Intercepts of the regression lines are not different from 0 and slopes of the regression lines are not different from 1 (observed vs. predicted) and 0 (studentized residuals vs. predicted) ($P > 0.55$) ($n = 51$).

References

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